

THE ROLE OF LINGUOCULTURAL COMPETENCE IN TEACHING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

Ruzmetova Dildora Adilbekovna

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor

Uzbek State University of World Languages

Email: druzmetova1974@g.mail.com

ORSID: 0009-0006-8967-0917

Abstract: The present article is devoted to the study of linguocultural competence in the process of teaching English as a foreign language. In contemporary language education, the issue of integrating language and culture has become one of the central methodological directions due to the growing importance of intercultural communication in the era of globalization. The author examines the relationship between language, culture, history, and national identity, emphasizing that successful communication in a foreign language requires not only grammatical and lexical knowledge but also an understanding of cultural values, traditions, customs, and behavioral norms of native speakers. The article analyzes the role of linguocultural approaches in developing learners' communicative competence and intercultural awareness. Special attention is paid to the cognitive approach, which allows learners to perceive language as a cultural and social phenomenon connected with human thinking and worldview. The author highlights the importance of using authentic materials, culturally oriented tasks, discussions, and interactive teaching methods in English classes.

Keywords: intercultural communication, globalization, competency-based approach, communicative competence, linguocultural method, cognitive approach, language evolution, extralinguistic factors, cultural awareness, language phenomenon.

INTRODUCTION:

The necessity of learning English has once again been underlined by the current rapid speed of globalization and the notable changes in the various links that exist between nations and people. Numerous linguistic, cultural, and pedagogical concerns are brought up by the growing global usage of English, and these concerns might be connected to how well pupils comprehend the language. Preparing linguistically competent experts who can interact with people from many backgrounds and use their knowledge in a variety of contexts is one of the main goals of English teachers.

One of the major problems with today's education system is the competencybased approach. Everyone needs a range of critical competencies (linguistic, social, cultural, and communicative) in order to successfully adapt and realize their potential as a young expert in the rapidly evolving modern world [1]. It is clear that many university graduates speak English at an inappropriate level, and even those who possess sufficient knowledge are unable to communicate professionally in the language. Furthermore, it is getting worse because some pupils don't know the fundamentals of the laws governing language evolution and the etymological traits of many terms.

Because they are unaware of the linguocultural facets of the English language as well as the cultures, traditions, and lifestyles of other countries, they occasionally neglect to comment on certain linguistic phenomena. It is important to see every foreign language as a system of social norms, conduct, and spiritual values in addition to linguistic rules. The fact that any live language evolves alongside its speech community—that is, its speakers—has long been understood. Regardless of place or time, language is essential to social interaction and history in all societies.

One of the main topics of study when studying English is probably the history of the language. Content and fundamental ideas A relatively recent field of study called linguoculturalology examines how the cultures of various countries have been preserved and represented in their languages. The two separate subfields of linguistics—sociolinguistics and culturology—have merged to form this relatively new area of linguistic study. The late 20th century saw a significant increase in interest in culturology and its genuine ascent from amateur conjecture to a legitimate scientific field. Sociolinguistic approaches are used in this field of study to explain a variety of linguistic occurrences [2].

When certain seemingly unexplained phenomena cannot be explained by language-internal data alone, this method is especially helpful. By examining linguistic units in relation to the nation's historical and social evolution across time, linguoculturalology aims to provide a wide understanding of the language as a complex system. According to Byram, people's social identities are an inevitable component of their social interactions with one another. This is taken into consideration in language instruction by the idea of "communicative competence," which emphasizes that language learners must learn not just how to use grammar correctly but also what constitutes "appropriate" discourse [5].

When teaching English, a linguocultural method emphasizes the semantic concept. From this perspective, learning English entails acquiring the language through its national concepts in addition to the conventional study of phonetics, syntax, and vocabulary. This makes it possible for the students to get interconnected ethnocultural knowledge about language, culture, and history. This leads to the development of linguacultural competence, a collection of unique abilities required for practical application. The Dictionary of English Language and Culture defines it as the capacity to carry out necessary tasks.

This means that a learner should be able to learn how to identify and relate a linguistic symbol's semantic content to the associative motive behind word choice. The notion of "competence" is defined in several Russian scientific works as an individual's intellectual and personal capacity for practical tasks, and "competence" is the content of the provided ability in the form of knowledge, skills, and aptitudes. Linguacultural studies address a wide range of language-related topics, including how culture shapes linguistic conceptions and the relationship between a word's cultural meaning and its linguistic symbol. Understanding cultural semantics, which arise from the interaction of two distinct domains - language and culture - is crucial. Interactions between language and culture are mutually reinforcing: language influences cultural interactions, and language influences cultural interactions. It should be mentioned that there are a lot of challenging and conflicting issues with the relationship between language and culture. One issue could arise when linguistic pieces' cultural information primarily gets some concealed significance.

METHODOLOGY

Language and history are inseparable, as are language and culture. Numerous details about how language functions in the speech community are included in the evolution of language. Extralinguistic and linguistic factors are the two categories into which the most commonly used

classification of language-related factors falls. In a strict sense, the phrase "extralinguistic" refers to a range of circumstances influencing various facets of human existence, such as psychological or physiological characteristics. However, first and foremost, extralinguistic factors include historical occurrences that are pertinent to the language's development, such as social organization, geographic expansion, migration, tribal mixing and separation, political and economic unity or disunity, interactions with other people, and the advancement of literature and culture. The linguistic condition and the language's evolution are determined by all of these external historical factors. Germanic invaders from the northwest coast of continental Europe arrived in Britain in the fifth and sixth centuries [3]. Some language units can be clarified by understanding people's histories, cultures, and ways of living. Fundamental aspects of linguocultural competency development. Students can gain appropriate comprehension and usage of the present language by taking a historical perspective to its phenomena. Scientific comprehension of the principles governing the present English language will be aided by knowledge of the laws governing language development, as well as the capacity to explain certain facts based on knowledge of the language's and the people's histories.

1. For this reason, students place a high value on the English language course's history. The primary assignments for this course are:

to identify the rules that govern the evolution of language as a particular system, that is, the process by which the phonetic, grammatical, and lexical components of the language structure fully develop and depend on one another;

to take into account the connection between the history of the English people and the history of the English language. This relationship is best illustrated by a number of facts about the evolution of the English language's lexicon;

to help students become more adept at recognizing specific linguistic phenomena and drawing connections between them throughout time. It is crucial for students since they will need to be able to correctly explain and scientifically support a specific language phenomenon in their future work;

to introduce students to certain factual material on the history of phonetics, grammar and vocabulary of the English language that will provide the basis for the development of the scientific outlook on the evolution of the language.

to identify the rules that govern the evolution of language as a particular system, that is, the process by which the phonetic, grammatical, and lexical components of the language structure fully develop and depend on one another;

to take into account the connection between the history of the English people and the history of the English language. This relationship is best illustrated by a number of facts about the evolution of the English language's lexicon;

to help students become more adept at recognizing specific linguistic phenomena and drawing connections between them throughout time. It is crucial for students since they will need to be able to correctly explain and scientifically support a specific language phenomenon in their future work;

to introduce students to certain factual material on the history of phonetics, grammar and vocabulary of the English language that will provide the basis for the development of the scientific outlook on the evolution of the language.

Students ensure that the English language is the result of multiple distinct phases of its evolution by tracing its history across various eras utilizing the actual material. The long and slow evolution of linguistic phenomena from earlier eras led to the creation of contemporary English. It is especially significant since many things that appear to be "deviations" or "wrong" in terms of language can actually be historical explanations for the remains of past laws.

Examples of modern English phenomena that can be explained scientifically include "wrong" plurals like man-men and foot-feet, as well as so-called nonstandard verb forms. Understanding the history of the English language is therefore essential to comprehending the structure of a modern language.

Language and culture are inseparable phenomena. According to E. Sapir [6],

"Language is a guide to social reality", while B. Whorf [7] stated that language shapes our perception of the world. Thus, developing communicative competence requires not only linguistic knowledge but also cultural awareness. In Uzbekistan and many other multilingual societies, fostering linguocultural proficiency is a key component of language education reform. D. Ruzmetova [9] emphasizes that *linguocultural competence allows learners to interpret the worldview embedded in the target language and interact effectively across cultures.*

2. The Concept of Linguocultural Proficiency

Linguocultural proficiency refers to a learner's ability to use language appropriately within a given cultural context. It includes:

- *Linguistic competence* – vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation;
- *Cultural competence* – knowledge of traditions, values, and social norms;
- *Intercultural communication skills* – understanding of cultural differences and the ability to adapt.

As V. A. Maslova [8] points out, "Linguocultural competence is a synthesis of language, mentality, and culture, reflected in the consciousness of an individual."

3. Methods of Enhancing Linguocultural Proficiency

3.1. Integrative Teaching Approach

Integrating cultural content into every language lesson helps students connect words with cultural meanings. Teachers can include:

- authentic texts, songs, and films; idiomatic expressions and proverbs;
- cultural discussions and comparisons.

3.2. Project-Based Learning

Projects on topics such as *"National Holidays," "Cultural Traditions,"* or *"Famous Historical Figures"* encourage students to research, present, and discuss cultural material in the target language. As G. Byram [5] notes, *"Intercultural communicative competence develops through reflection on one's own culture and comparison with others."*

3.3. Role-Playing and Simulation

Role-plays based on real-life cultural scenarios (e.g., greeting rituals, dining etiquette, job interviews) immerse students in authentic communication situations.

This method enhances pragmatic awareness and empathy.

3.4. Use of Multimedia and Digital Tools

Modern technologies — videos, podcasts, online forums, and virtual exchanges — expose learners to diverse linguistic and cultural contexts. Interactive platforms like eTwinning or Tandem allow cross-cultural communication in real time.

3.5. Comparative Linguocultural Analysis

Comparing idioms, gestures, humor, and communication styles between native and target cultures fosters deeper cultural understanding and tolerance. For example, studying how compliments or apologies differ across cultures helps avoid miscommunication.

4. The Role of the Teacher

Teachers play a crucial role as mediators between languages and cultures. According to D. Ruzmetova, “A linguocultural educator not only teaches words but also the meanings and values behind them.” Teachers should model cultural sensitivity, create inclusive learning environments, and encourage reflection on cultural experiences [9].

RESULTS

Developing linguocultural proficiency is essential for preparing globally competent learners. Effective methods include integrative instruction, project-based learning, role-play, digital tools, and intercultural comparison. Language teachers must continuously enrich their cultural awareness and pedagogical techniques to help students communicate meaningfully in the global community.

Intercultural communication is emphasized as the most crucial component of human society's integration in the contemporary global economic and cultural arena. The challenge of establishing the framework for teaching intercultural communication increases students' willingness to study a foreign language and gives linguocultural competency development particular significance. Given these conditions, understanding the English language's past is becoming increasingly crucial. The goal of developing students' linguocultural competence is to help them understand their own national or social origin, the place and function of their national culture, the history of the target language, the traditions and customs of the people, the spiritual values of the people in the world, and their country's ability to represent itself. This particular course engages students in linguistic studies and research with the goal of educating them about humanistic principles.

Students who possess linguistic competence are able to undertake exploratory work, write and speak in a foreign language, comprehend and discuss cultural and socioeconomic aspects of the target language, and create an oral report on a chosen subject. Students are methodically taught the most comprehensive history and universal cultural values of humanity through the study of foreign languages. It contributes to the development of national identity, citizenship, humanism, tolerance, and respect for national and global culture. It also helps to create a genuine opportunity for students to become familiar with universal spiritual and moral values as well as world and national culture in order to comprehend the issues and realities of the modern world.

The development of intercultural communicative competence and communication culture is facilitated by experimental work. To determine the impact of experimental activity on students'

development of experimental linguocultural competence, diagnostic tests were employed. The following dynamics were discovered by the experiment's test results:

students evaluate interpersonal communication norms; students study and understand their own cultural values;

students engage in real intercultural communication activities.

1. One of the most important values and educational objectives nowadays is the issue of intercultural learning in the study of English language history.

2. More than two languages and cultures—native and non-native—are the foundation for linguistic and cultural competency. The foundation for developing linguocultural competency is the study of national culture.

3. Student-centered pedagogy serves as the foundation for the psychological and educational circumstances that help students develop their linguocultural competency.

4. Language proficiency has a strong educational impact on the development of linguocultural competency.

CONCLUSION

The findings indicate that there is a need to modify the requirements for pupils. It is believed that a person's culture is a crucial aspect of their human potential. Since communication is fundamental to human existence, it is also a component of culture. The psychological preparedness of the student to communicate (interest, motivation, and lack of fear of the language barrier) as well as a certain level of verbal skills, language content, and—above all—the required amount of sociocultural knowledge of the spoken language are all considered aspects of cross-cultural competence. The three primary domains of competency are motivational, pragmatic, and cognitive.

REFERENCES

1. Awareness in Language Teaching. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. Kramsch, C. 1993. Context and Culture in Language Teaching. Oxford: Oxford University Press. McConachy, T., Golubeva, I., and Wagner, M. 2022.
2. Procedia–Social and Behavioral Sciences, Vol.112:532-537. Baker, W. 2022. Intercultural and Transcultural.
3. Practical Introduction for Teachers. Language Policy Division. Directorate of School, Out-of-school and Higher Education. DGIV Council of Europe, Strasbourg: 4. Intercultural Learning in Language Education and Beyond: Evolving Concepts, Perspectives and Practices. Bristol: Multilingual Matters.
5. Byram M., Gribkova B., Starkey H., (2002). Developing the Intercultural Dimension in Language Teaching.
5. Khazratova G.Sh. Intercultural teaching methods of english at higher education establishments, Xorazm mamun Academy -axborotnomasi, 2022-11/3
6. Sapir, E. (1921). *Language: An Introduction to the Study of Speech*.
7. Whorf, B. L. (1956). *Language, Thought, and Reality*.

8. Maslova, V. A. (2001). *Linguocultural Studies*. Moscow.
9. Ruzmetova D. Преодоления интерференции в условиях многоязычия: на примере узбекского, русского и английского языков в Узбекистане //Science and innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. А6. – С. 599-604.
10. Adilbekovna R. D. Challenges in Teaching English as a Specific Purpose //Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 93-97.
11. Ruzmetova Dildora Adilbekovna 2025. THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING. Международный журнал научных исследователей. 11, 1 (май 2025), 686–688.
12. Ruzmetova D.A., Abdullayeva Z.N. INGLIZ TILIDAGI ILMIY TERMINLARNI IDROK ETISHNING PSIXOLOGIK JIHATLARI //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2024. – Т. 5. – №. CSPU Conference 1. – С. 366
13. Рuzметова Д. А. Об экономической потенциальной лексике //Молодой ученый. – 2012. – №. 4. – С. 455-457.